

Saponification Kinetics of Dioxyacetic Esters of some Bisphenols

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The hydrolysis of ordinary esters are catalysed by a number of agents such as acids, bases and enzymes. According to Ingold¹ and Laidler and Landaskroener², the rate of a reaction is expected to increase with increasing dielectric constant of the system, while Parker³ and Roberts⁴ observed that the rate constant decreases under the conditions of increasing dielectric constant of the medium. Limited work has been done on the saponification kinetics of diesters⁵. This prompted us to study the saponification kinetics of dioxyacetic esters of some bisphenols.

Results and Discussion

Base-catalysed bimolecular acyl fission mechanism is the most common type of hydrolysis when the alcoholic part involved is primary or secondary. The rate of the reaction depends on the concentration of the ester and on the concentration of base, i.e. rate = k [Ester][OH⁻]. The reaction takes place through acyl oxygen fission.

The second order rate constant (k) of alkaline hydrolysis of methyl ester of 3 in MeOH-H₂O (90 : 10, JICS-8

v/v) system at 30° is reported in Table 1. The second order rate constant data on methyl, ethyl and propyl esters of 1, 2 and 3 in MeOH-H₂O and dioxane-H₂O system at four different temperature, viz. 30, 35, 40 and 45° showed increase in rate constant with increase in temperature. The rate constant values for all the esters in MeOH-H₂O system were found larger than that of dioxane-H₂O system due to preferred formation of more polar transition state in MeOH-H₂O of high dielectric constant (~37) than that of dioxane-H₂O of low dielectric constant (~9.8). Thus, MeOH-H₂O system is approximately 3.8 times more polar than that of dioxane-H₂O system. A comparative order of the rate constants is propyl ester > ethyl ester > methyl ester at all the temperatures studied except esters of 3 in MeOH-H₂O system where the order is ethyl ester > methyl ester > propyl ester above 30°. If there is any substituent in acyl or alkyl portion of the ester, it attracts electrons towards itself and thereby tend to increase the positive charge on the carbonyl carbon and therefore facilitates the attack by the hydroxyl ions. During the formation of the intermediate there occurs an increase in the extent of over-crowding due to change in hybridisation from sp^2 to sp^3 . The larger the R group the more will be steric retardation. For a given ester of 1-3, the rate constant order

TABLE 1—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANT (k) OF ALKALINE HYDROLYSIS OF METHYL ESTER OF **3** IN MeOH-H₂O (90:10, v/v) SYSTEM[Ester] = 0.005 M, [OH] = 0.01 M, a = 5 ml, Temp. = 30°

Time (min)	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90
k ($\cdot 10^3$ ml ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)	2.73	2.75	2.72	2.69	2.77	2.72	2.74	2.70	2.72

is $3 > 1 > 2$ at all temperatures in MeOH-H₂O system, that means that steric retardation is less in **3** and more in **2**. Thus the substituent in acyl and alkyl portion of esters influences the rate of the reaction. The causes are not clear for the reverse orders of rate constants in the esters of **3** above 30° in MeOH-H₂O system.

The dielectric constant of the medium and solvation phenomenon play important role on the rate of the reaction and hence the rate constant values are expected to be more in MeOH-H₂O system. The dioxane has two lone-pairs and thereby has a tendency for hydrogen bonding with a number of water molecules more than that of methanol. Dioxane by its considerable entrance in secondary solvation sheath of HO⁻ ion will contribute to its greater solvation. Thus both the solvation and the dielectric constant changes appear to act simultaneously in affecting the rate of the reaction. The OH⁻ ion is likely to be more and more desolvated in MeOH-H₂O system compared to dioxane-H₂O system and this will result in the lowering of

activation energy and hence an increase in the rate constant. This observation is in tune with that expressed by Parker³ and Roberts⁴.

The energy of activation ($E_a^\ddagger$) and the frequency factor (A) were determined according to Arrhenius equation. The other thermodynamic activation parameters, such as $\Delta H^\ddagger$, $\Delta S^\ddagger$ and $\Delta G^\ddagger$ were determined for both the solvent systems at all the temperatures. A typical data at 35° are reported in Table 2. The reaction rate constant is governed by $\Delta G^\ddagger$ and it is dependent on the nature of the solvent, the nature of the ions and the ionic strength of the solution. It is observed experimentally that the values of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ are almost constant for a given ester but different for different esters at all the temperatures although their $\Delta G^\ddagger$ values are almost constant. It is evident from Table 2 that the values of $\Delta S^\ddagger$ is negative and large in magnitude, indicating that the transition state is in increasing ordered state compared to the individual molecules. The constant values of $\Delta G^\ddagger$ can be explained by the fact

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR THE ESTERS OF **1-3** AT 35°

Ester	R	$\Delta H^\ddagger$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)		$\Delta S^\ddagger$ (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)		$\Delta G^\ddagger$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	
		MeOH-H ₂ O	Dioxane-H ₂ O	MeOH-H ₂ O	Dioxane-H ₂ O	MeOH-H ₂ O	Dioxane-H ₂ O
1	Me	15.1	15.9	-166.0	-161.0	91.6	92.5
	Et	11.2	9.0	-194.0	-215.1	91.6	92.9
	Pr	10.1	15.2	-201.5	-167.6	91.2	92.5
2	Me	19.5	9.0	-133.9	-216.4	92.1	93.3
	Et	15.5	10.5	-162.2	-202.0	91.6	92.0
	Pr	8.0	12.1	-216.3	-188.4	91.2	91.6
3	Me	11.1	12.5	-191.3	-183.9	90.4	91.6
	Et	10.8	5.6	-193.1	-234.9	90.0	91.2
	Pr	5.3	2.6	-234.6	-237.8	90.8	90.8

that the environmental compensation of the order-disorder states are governed by $\Delta H^\ddagger$ values at a given temperature.

The experimental results are in excellent agreement with the general mechanism proposed through acyl oxygen fission². The large negative values of $\Delta S^\ddagger$ and small values of A indicate that the formation of intermediate compound is the rate-determining step.

Experimental

Dioxyacetic acids and their methyl, ethyl and propyl esters of bisphenols were synthesised and purified⁶ according to the reported methods⁶. Methanol and dioxane (laboratory grade) were fractionally distilled prior to use. Permanganate-treated double-distilled water was used. Each ester solution (0.005 M) in MeOH-H₂O and dioxane-H₂O (90 : 10 v/v) and 0.01 M NaOH solution in double-distilled water were prepared. The kinetic measurements were carried out by determining the concentration of alkali volumetrically as a function of time. Equal volumes of the ester and alkali (50 ml each) were thermostated at required temperature. The two solutions were quickly mixed and the mixture was allowed to react for definite time interval (10 min). Aliquots (5 ml) was then withdrawn

and titrated against standard 0.01 N HCl using phenolphthalein as indicator.

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